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Oke-Ite And Ritual-Killing As Correlates Of Crude Intelligence Among Youths In Anambra State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

In this age and time when quest for quick money is rampant and the phenomenon is pressing down societal values, a study of oke-ite and ritual-killing as correlates of crude intelligence becomes necessary. Anambra State residents are mostly traders and as such, the rustling and bustling of people seem to have disposed the youths of this State to the quest for quick money at all cost. The aim of this study is to explore the relationship of oke-ite and ritual-killing to crude intelligence in the perception of Anambra youths. The study employed a mixed-method model, using case study, descriptive survey and correlational designs. Six research questions were posed and three null hypotheses were crafted, to guide the study. The sample, through strategic multistage technique, was drawn from six towns in the three Senatorial Districts of the State (N = 1,200). A researcher-developed instrument, termed OIRK-Q (oke-ite and ritual-killing questionnaire), was developed and validated for data collection. The instrument contained 30 items. Descriptive statistics of sum, frequency, percentage and mean were used in the data analyses and interpretations. Further probabilities were tested using tools from Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS), namely Pearson Moment Coefficient, Multivariate, Independent T-test, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and Bivariate Correlations. Major findings showed that: 1) youths rated poorly of oke-ite as crime (N=550; 45.8%), but rated ritual-killing highly as a crime (N=1,199; 99.9%); 2) practitioners of oke-ite are rated high in their possession of crude-intelligence (N=1,027; 85.6%), but poorly of those who engage in ritual-killing (N=200;17.8%). Meanwhile participants in their responses revealed that criminals are intelligent (N=1,182; 98.5%). 3) Male and female participants agreed in many item-questions regarding oke-ite and crude intelligence, but differ significantly in their agreeability about ritual-killing and crude intelligence (mean diff = 4.46; t = 10.38; df = 1,198; p-value = .000. 4) Although distinctive difference existed between oke-ite and ritual-killing in their correlations to crude intelligence, the final result showed that oke-ite and ritual-killing in interaction, minimally correlate with crude intelligence ($F_{1,32}=1.72$; $mean^2=123.69$; p-value=.008). A major recommendation is that the government should checkmate the activities of traditional native doctors who promote ritual crimes of all sorts.

Keywords: oke-ite, ritual-killing, crude intelligence, Anambra youths, traditional native doctors

INTRODUCTION

Crime dates back to human existence. The day Cain killed Abel in the Christian Old Testament Bible, as well as Asian traditional and religious history, crime entered into human history. Regulation of crime exists according to societies and communities. With the origin of human rights enshrined in the United Nations Declarations, Member Nations have begun to develop national constitutions and codes, in line to meet the goals and objectives of United Nations. From then, certain ritual killings in traditional settings

automatically become crimes. In fact, human killing for ritual or any purpose of customary fulfilment of any sort is considered a first class crime. In this study, the researcher may use the terms of *ritual crime* and *ritual killing* interchangeably with liberty.

Ritualistic crimes refer to criminal activities that have a ritual belief or tradition attached to them (Isiaka & Nasirudeen, 2018). Ritual crime is a type of crime that involves different people or group of people's culture or religion. It is mostly committed under a united common social, religious, or political philosophy. A recent study has posited that the age mostly involved in ritual crimes falls within the brackets of 18 to 25 years (Gale, 2005). This age bracket constitutes the studied population of this research. The two variables in this study, namely *oke-ite* and *ritual-killing* are considered ritual crimes, with *oke-ite* being more of fraud unless human parts are used. Crimes are ritualistic when the process and product of such are involving rites targeted at the destruction of life and living things before or during the crime committal (Udoye, 2022).

Ritual crime as noted by Obineke (2008) is committed in every country, though the methods used by the perpetrators are, expectedly, different in nations, given socio-cultural and political contexts. Given differences in the societies some ritual-killings are more subtle than others. Ritual crimes are crimes that include abduction, killing, maiming, butchering of humans and severing body parts for the purposes of seeking wealth, magical/political power, longevity, and other self-centered reasons. In this study, any sort of harming human body for the purpose of rituals is considered ritual-killing, which is a crime, in any socio-psychological stance. All the societies of the United Nations see human killing of any sort as a violent crime against humanity.

From time of ages, when humanity suffered from ignorance and superstitions, human beings were sacrificed for religious and spiritual purposes on the excuse of seeking solutions to problems affecting households and communities. It could also be for appeasing the gods and supporting deities. More recently the dynamics have changed. People are not just killed and sacrificed but are reportedly butchered for even more criminal reasons outside the realm of traditional humanity. This is something more perturbing than ignorance and superstition. It could even relate to psychosis and suggests other psychosocial damages to human brain. This unpleasant situation has become, scary to say, a regular practice in Nigeria that is not limited to age and gender (Gale, 2005; Munthali, 2006; Obineke, 2008).

Ritual crimes extend to killing humans and severing their body parts 'for food and for sale'. Victims of ritual crime could be assaulted before they are killed for rituals. Ritual crimes and their reported occurrences have assumed worrisome dimensions. They are no more regarded as bizarre phenomenon as they have come to be recognized amongst youth making everyone aware of their realities (Obineke, 2008). Recently in Nigeria, ritual crimes have risen immensely and to disturbing velocity (Obineke, 2008; Mcaioh, 2017). These authors agree that the rise in the menace has majorly been attributed to the get-rich-quick syndrome attitude of youths and subsequent display of prosperity.

In ancient times, ritual killings were alien to some regions of Nigeria, except those carried out to appease the gods. These included people offering their dear ones. In those days, the practice of ritual-killing became extensive and grew worse to using of strangers, innocent people and even young ones for rituals (Obineke, 2008). Today, the practice is majorly attributed to acquisition of power, wealth, longevity and prestige. As quest for position and power increases, so is the belief that success in this, requires spiritual defence to avoid assassination or conquest by opponents. It is not surprising that some Nigerians in their various fields of endeavours are involved in the practice of ritual crimes of all sorts (Evelyn, 2017; Isaac, 2017).

From the birth of humanity, desires for gains over pains have simultaneously been in human nature. These desires, according to psychologists, can only be contained and curbed by strong ego, well-developed superego, and healthy developed personality if the desire could lead the person to commit crimes. It is not incorrect to say that every adult human would desire for power and wealth, but only the morally weak would want the acquisitions of such at all cost, even if lives should be sacrificed. According to Aghawenu (2020), ritual-killing stems from people's endless hunt for wealth. Unfortunately, industrialization with its attendant capitalism has made nature's greediness for power worse than ever. Isaac (2017) observed that

the menace of ritual-killing has become a big modern capitalist business and human parts are sold across the country. Ritual-killings have recently been included among the foremost security challenges in Nigeria.

Ritual-killers mostly abduct, butcher and sever human body for the purpose of money and or malice. Aside from being a grave felony, ritual-killing constitutes a failure on the part of the government to uphold the fundamental rights of its citizens, with respect to life and dignity of human persons. News and records report many lives being lost. Countless victims have become mentally disordered while families of victims have suffered from after-effects of psychosomatic traumas (Salihu, Isiaka & Abdulziz, 2019; Munthali, 2009). Records of children being orphaned rise, and scores of parents becoming parentless with loss of their children increase. Every crime has ripple effect in the societies. Shock and anguish that accompany loss of loved ones through ritual crimes have sent many to untimely death. Victims and relatives of victim could develop tendencies towards suicide. Victimization through ritual crime impact psychological being greatly. These psychological maladies often result into untimely death. The shock and trauma of ritual crime disturb the human equilibrium of the psyche (Munthali, 2009).

The most recent crime statistics released in 2018 by the Force Criminal Investigation Department of the Nigeria Police revealed that the incidence of ritual-killings is multiplying (Classified, 2018). No State in the Country can speak of complete immunity from ritual-killings, or boast of freedom from their perpetrators (Romoke, 2018). The operations of ritual killers are not confined to certain towns or villages. They are neither restricted to specific tribes, ethnic groups, nor are they known with particular gender or socio-economic class. Media, newspapers, and crime reports have not excused any geopolitical zones from ritual-killings (Adegbamigbe, 2008). Nigeria is claimed to be predominantly religious and believed to be mostly robust in religious practices. Yet, these qualities of religiosity have failed to save any state from charge of ritual-killing (Adegbamigbe, 2008).

Information, media and scholarly articles report that menace of ritual-killings has reached its climax following the onset of a cannibalistic dimension where humans murder and eat their fellows (Romoke, 2018; Nwaka, 2020; Oriabure, 2023) . Nigerian communities have reported series of cases where victims were not only murdered but butchered with their body parts used for meals (Evelyn, 2017). There was a case of a kidnapper suspect 'Roland Peter' who was arrested together with his accomplices when he was on the verge of eating meals prepared with the intestines of his victims (Evelyn, 2017; Mcaioh, 2017). It may sound disgusting and horrifying, but that is just how degrading humans have debased. There are suspected vampires in the midst of human societies who not only drink human blood but eat their raw flesh.

Committal of ritual crimes is enough to suggest critical damage on the cognitive templates and affective platforms of the perpetrators. It is unimaginable how a sane human could manage to hold a weapon to kill and butcher fellow human into slices and still goes to function normally. It is worse when they prepare fellows for soup (Evelyn, 2017; Mcaioh, 2017). This is just completely ridiculous and outside humanity. According to Oyewole (2016), ignorance, abject poverty and lowest thinking have pushed many people to indulge in money rituals and assist ritual criminals with kidnapping. The rising cases of ritual crimes of oke-ite, rape, killing in Nigeria have become perturbing events. Ritual crimes, often times involving killing of innocent people, have left Nigeria as a nation with great concern. Event of ritual crimes have led citizens into fear of their lives. The perpetrators of ritual crimes could not be less intelligent than average of their age counterparts. This assumption needs to be tested, and this is one of the reasons for this study. If considered intelligent, ritual criminals can be helped to unlearn the crimes.

Studies on ritual crimes include the research works of Nwankwo and Okolie-Osomene (2016) as well as Oyewole (2016). Nwankwo and Okolie-Osemene (2016) revealed that ritual murder produced 18 deaths each in Lagos and Ogun State in 2014. Oyewole (2016) on the other hand reported that the ritual-motivated kidnapping could be grouped under two categories, namely faith and materialism. These authors found that ritual crimes are forming the highest security threats in criminal analyses of kidnapping within the country.

Statement of the Problem

Observation has indicated that ritual-killings have come to stay in Nigeria as well as oke-ite phenomenon. Important questions asked in this study are, “*How, in reality, are oke-ite and ritual-killing prevailing?*” and “*What are the characteristic peculiarities of these phenomena?*” If oke-ite practice is considered a fraud, and ritual-killing a critical legal offence, the question is, “*How come the practices of oke-ite and ritual-killing are still on the rise in Anambra?*” The researcher believes that considerable attention needs to be given to these variables and their practices in the State. In the same vein, it is a general opinion that criminals are intelligent persons. The more sophisticated an executed crime is, the more sophisticated the criminal’s intelligence is. It is understood that every criminal is more or less above average in intellectual analysis.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study is to examine *oke-ite* and ritual-killing as correlates of crude-intelligence among youths in Anambra State. The specific objectives of the study are to:

- 1) Describe the prevalence of oke-ite and ritual-killing among youths in Anambra State, Nigeria.
- 2) Determine characteristics of oke-ite among youths in Anambra State, Nigeria.
- 3) Determine characteristics of ritual-killing among youths in Anambra State, Nigeria.
- 4) Find how male and female participants compare in their response to the study of oke-ite and ritual-killing in correlation to crude-intelligence among youths in Anambra State, Nigeria.
- 5) Investigate relationship between oke-ite and ritual-killing among youths in Anambra State, Nigeria.
- 6) Ascertain how oke-ite and ritual-killing practices together correlate with crude-intelligence in the study of youths in Anambra State, Nigeria.

1.4 Significance of the Study

This study is significant, theoretically and practically.

Theoretically, the study would add to the current body of knowledge about ritual-killing, oke-ite and other similar crimes, particularly contributing insights about the youth involvement in ritual crimes.

Practically, the findings and recommendations of this present study would help the government to formulate and implement policies that could target at revitalizing community based project and private sectors’ participation towards the welfare of the youth in efforts to curtail ritual crimes.

This study would provide a template which the policy makers could use to formulate effective policies related to breaking the social ills of oke-ite and ritual-killing.

Hopefully, the study would also provide a base for further research aimed at documenting the influence of spiritual belief on the perpetration of ritual crimes among the youths in Anambra State.

1.5 Scope of the Study

This study was conducted in six Towns of Anambra State, two of which were each selected from the three Senatorial Zones of the State. The phenomena of oke-ite and ritual-killing are suspected to be prevalent in the State. The research focused specifically on Anambra State of South-Eastern Nigeria, where hustling and bustling of Nnewi and Onitsha are predisposing the young person’s to the seeking of riches and wealth at all cost. Ritual-killing is contained in this study as a crime closely matching the prevalence of oke-ite in the State.

1.6 Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study.

- 1) How prevalent are oke-ite and ritual-killing among youths in Anambra State, Nigeria?
- 2) What are the characteristics of oke-ite among youths in Anambra State, Nigeria?
- 3) What are the characteristics of ritual-killing among youths in Anambra State, Nigeria?
- 4) How do male and female youths compare in their response to the study of oke-ite, ritual-killing and crude intelligence?
- 5) How does oke-ite relate to ritual-killing in their practices among youths in Anambra State, Nigeria?

- 6) How do oke-ite and ritual-killing practices correlate with crude-intelligence among youths in Anambra State, Nigeria?

1.7 Research Hypotheses

Three research hypotheses were formulated to test probabilities in the study. They were nulled and tested at significance level of $p\text{-value} < .05$

H₀₁: There was no significant difference between how male and female participants compare in their mean responses to OIRK-Q in Anambra State.

H₀₂: There was no significant relationship between oke-ite and ritual-killing and among youths in Anambra State, Nigeria.

H₀₃: Oke-ite and ritual-killing have no significant correlations with crude-intelligence in the responses of OIRK items among the studied youths in Anambra State, Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Framework

Oke-ite

Oke-ite, a term that literally means *great-pot* is a charm. Unlike other charms and amulets, oke-ite is prepared by the 'fetish priests' and mostly kept in his custody. Oke-ite could be kept in the custody of the preparer for the client or carried home by the client. The essence of keeping oke-ite by the fetish priest is to ensure proper maintenance of providing the desires of the gods as when needed. Oke-ite is a concoction generally prepared with human parts, animals and herbs gathered in a mud pot. It is usually dedicated to a particular god after being concocted. This god is believed to be powerful enough to give whatever is asked of it. The client could ask for money, pleasure, power or fame. It is presumed that the faith of the client and the concoction condiments of oke-ite make for the potency it claims to have. Oke-ite comes in diverse forms such as *Ibobo*, *Uduakommiri*, *NwunyeIte*, an so on. Customers and clients of this fetish practice believe that this sort of charm accelerates a person's progress, therefore defiling the natural law.

Oke-ite is believed by customers and clients to be a panacea to all challenges and key to unlocking unto great fortune (Okeke, Nwosu & Chinazom, 2023). Customers and clients of oke-ite are indoctrinated into believing an unimaginable "greatness" ascribed to it. This is why some scholars have termed oke-ite a fraud that has washed away the psychological prowess of the young people (Okeke, Nwosu, Chinazom 2023; Emmanuel, 2022). Under the pretext of cultural revival and the renaissance of the traditional religion, fetish priests of oke-ite masquerade as ministers of the local deities. They exploit their clients and customers with false claims to possessing excessive powers (Petrus, 2007).

Ritual-killing

Ritual-killing is a criminal act of killing human beings and animals for the purpose of sacrifice or sheer wickedness. This act could involve use of whole being or parts. The killing could be physical or psychosocial. Popular opinion has suggested that most ritual-killing done in Nigeria are done for money ritual. Licensed abattoirs where domestic animals are slaughtered for purposes of providing meat for human consumption are not included in the concept of ritual-killing discussed in this study.

As early as in the second half of 20th Century, Igbinovia (1988) and Awolalu (1979) exposed the onset of this disturbing trajectory of a menacing sociological dynamism in Nigeria. It was as if it was nothing to worry about. This is because Nigerians have a natural way of maintaining equanimity even in the face of psychosocial and socio-political pandemonium that would cause members of any nation in the West to go berserk. Isiaka and Nasirudeen (2018); Salihu, and others (2019); as well as Aghawenu (2020; posited that society and government could not be fully exonerated from being part of the reasons for the rise. These scholars are of the opinion that ritual-killing are on the rise because of government's negligence, motivation for quick money and pleasure, as well as societies' welcoming wealth without asking questions as to the means of the wealth.

Crude Intelligence

Crude intelligence, opposite of which is refined intelligence, refers to a basic, unsophisticated form of problem-solving ability or mental processing that relies on instinct, raw calculation, or direct methods rather than nuanced understanding or refined cognitive abilities. This intelligence type originates in the field of Crime Sciences, basing its formulation on the Theory of Multiple Intelligence of Howard Gardner (1983, 1993^a, 1993^b, 1999). This type of intelligence focuses on practical, straightforward approaches to situations, often lacking in subtlety, moral creativity, or depth logical analysis. It may involve quick, sometimes unrefined judgment, with an emphasis on immediate results over long-term planning or deeper analysis.

In the later part of 20th Century, Howard Gardner (1983) opined in his *Frame of Mind* that humans think and problem-solve through gifted ways of intellectual capabilities and abilities. He called it *Multiple Intelligences* (Gardner, 1993). The theorist suggests that humans could be gifted or have learnt any or a combination of these Intelligences, namely Verbal-Linguistic, Logico-Mathematical, Musical, Bodily-Kinaesthetic, Interpersonal, Intrapersonal, and Naturalistic. Shortly before the onset of 21st Century, Gardner (1999) added the Existential Intelligence, still being researched and developed. When any of these intelligences become thwarted, destructive, lacks wisdom, is emptied of reality, it turns into *crude intelligence*. Crude intelligence bears its terminological origin following the events of September 11th 2001 bombing of Twin Tower in the United States by Osama Bin Laden and gang.

Crude Intelligence could be gifted, or it could be learned. The easy possibility of it being thwarted and used to harm others makes it be termed *crude*. Some authors in Learning Sciences use the term *inverse intelligence* to describe this kind of intelligence in the society (Udoye, 2022; Tepperman, 2010). Crude intelligence refers to a basic, unsophisticated form of problem-solving ability or mental processing that relies on instinct, raw calculation, or systematic direct methods rather than nuanced understanding of refined cognitive abilities. Crude intelligence focuses on practical, straightforward approaches to situations. It is often lacks subtlety, creativity, or depth in reasoning. It may involve quick, sometimes unrefined judgment, with an emphasis on immediate results over long-term planning or deeper analysis.

Ritualism

Ritualism refers to the practice of engaging in formalized, repetitive actions or ceremonies, often connected to religious or cultural traditions. These rituals can be symbolic and may have specific meanings or purposes, such as worship, celebration, or honouring important events. Rituals involve “activating spiritual powers, whether they are gods, spirits, or ancestors, in order to achieve a beneficent result” (Fontaine, 2011). These activities are often conducted in secret (and sometimes in the open, depending on the type and purpose) and in special places. Rituals, according to Bell (1997) are usually characterized by strict adherence to traditional practice and values, sacerdotal symbolism, and sequential performance. Fontaine (2011) maintains that a vital component in a ritual sacrifice is the identification of a particular object(s) that becomes a sacred symbol(s) through a process of sanctification. Generally, rituals take different forms and are performed for different purposes or motives. Among the widely known types of traditional rituals in Africa and/or reasons why rituals are performed are coronation rites, rites of passage, commemorative (festival) rites, and mitigation of affliction rites.

However, in a sociological context, ritualism can also describe when individuals strictly follow societal rules or routines without necessarily believing in their underlying goals. They adhere to the established norms and structures for the sake of conformity, even when they do not expect the desired outcomes. In the context of crime or unethical behaviour, ritualism may refer to actions taken for symbolic purposes, often based on superstitions or beliefs, like the practice of "money rituals" (as in oke-ite). Ritual crime involves performing specific acts believed to bring wealth or power, without proper and commensurate hard work, sometimes involving dangerous and criminal activities. Scholars have associated ritualism to incidences of kidnapping in Nigeria (Olulowo, Babwale, & Anani, 2021)

Retreatism

Retreatism is a concept in sociology, particularly in Robert K. Merton's strain theory, which describes a form of behaviour where individuals reject both the cultural goals of society and the accepted means to

achieve those goals. Retreatists withdraw from society's expectations and norms, opting for a lifestyle that avoids the pressures of conformity altogether. Unlike other forms of social deviance, retreatism is characterized by withdrawal rather than rebellion or innovation. Retreatists neither attempt to achieve success through socially acceptable means nor pursue success in alternative ways. They may engage in escapist behaviours, such as substance abuse, living off-grid, or complete disengagement from societal roles.

Fetishism

Fetishism refers to the attribution of inherent or supernatural powers to an object, material, or entity, which becomes the focus of obsessive attention or worship. It has various meanings in different fields such as anthropology, religion, sociology, and psychology. Below is a breakdown of fetishism's different contexts. Fetishism is a way of attributing a mystical or magical quality to objects produced, consumed or used by the people. There are three types of fetishism reviewed in this study, namely Cultural, Marxist and Psychological.

Theoretical Review

Demonology Theory

It is difficult to trace the origin and author of Demonology. This theoretical study, experienced in the human society, dates back to human existence. Demonology, traditionally, refers to the belief in the existence and influence of demons, semi-demons and their human agents, in the human activities and affairs. This theory has been historically used to explain various phenomena, including mental illness such as schizophrenia, paranormal; life misfortunes; and deviant behaviour in society. In a contemporary context, the theory can be applied to understand certain social behaviours, including ritual crimes of all sorts of attributed trait psychology (Trefilova, 2020; Ziolkowski, 1991). This application is most relevant in cultures where spiritual beliefs and supernatural explanations for success and failure are prevalent. Demonology is found in African cultures for the fact that relationship to beneficial and harming spirits in the gods.

In relation to oke-ite and ritual-killing among youths, Demonology offers insights into how cultural beliefs surrounding spirits, demons, and rituals influence behaviour. Additionally, it provides a framework for understanding how these beliefs intersect with the concept of crude intelligence, where youths might engage in unethical or supernatural practices to attain wealth and status. Demonology uses a native intelligence to operate in the faith construct of the people. What the people demonize becomes effective in their daily life experiences (Tepperman, 2010).

Social Learning Theory

The study is based on social learning theory, pioneered by psychologist Albert Bandura(1977), particularly the principle of observational learning termed *modelling* (Chukwura, 2009). Social Learning Theory, as developed by Albert Bandura, posits that people learn behaviours, values, and attitudes through *observation, imitation, and modelling*.

According to this theory, individuals can learn both positive and negative behaviours by observing others within their social environment. Bandura emphasized the role of observational learning, where individuals internalize behaviours by watching others, especially those who are perceived as role models or influential figures. In the context of this study, Social Learning Theory helps explain how these deviant practices are learned, normalized, and perpetuated among youths, particularly in environments where cultural beliefs, peer influence, and socioeconomic pressures are strong.

Classical Theory of Crime

According to Classical Theory, people act based on their own conditioned self-interest, and crime is viewed as a rational decision made when the cognitive construct is used to outweigh the costs. Classical theory of crime is biological and genetic. This is born out of the Ivan Pavlov's (1849 – 1936) Classical Conditioning and later developed by B. F. Skinner's (1984) two-factor theory of operant conditioning in behaviourism. These theorists position is that human crime can become classically conditioned in their practice of certain behaviours as though those behaviours have been wired into them from birth. Classical

theory of crime explains the idea of serviced behaviours in crimes. Motives, drives, interests, desires and other innate tendencies in people can predispose individuals and hardwire in them the need to commit crimes. Ritual crimes have more of these tendencies because of its nature to perpetrate in reoccurrence and maintenance.

Theory of Strain by Robert Merton (1938)

The social conditions and economic realities dictate who succeeds, that is, the structural arrangement limits the rights and opportunities of some members in the society. Consequently, different individuals will experience a different level of strain as they try to achieve the goals. These variations will, in turn, produce some pressures that typically result in various kinds of outcomes (lawlessness). Merton's assumption is based on the principle that if an individual is thwarted in his or her efforts to obtain the culturally defined goals using institutionalized means, he or she may be tempted to achieve them through a variety of illegal means, that is, individuals who are frustrated by their inability to fulfil the American dream are likely to channel their energies into unlawful activities as ways of attaining these goals.

Merton gave five major ways individuals or groups may respond to the situation of strain. According to him, some groups will conform to the existing standards and values by accepting the goals and are determined, despite the constraint, to achieve them using legitimate means (conformist), while others will opt for rather deviant approaches by accepting the legitimate goals but inventing illegitimate means to achieve them (innovationists), rejecting the goals but continuing to use the legitimate means (ritualists), rejecting both the goals and the means (retreatists), or rejecting the goals and substituting them with something entirely different, and adopting whatever means they deem fit to achieve their goals (rebels). Merton's structural strain theory basically focused on how the structure of a society induces or motivates individuals or groups to violate the social norms. According to Merton (1938), *Strain* exists when the society emphasizes socially defined goals rather than the means. For instance, when one becomes wealthy and the community does not care how the money is made, goes ahead to honour the one with chieftaincy and honorary titles, strain occurs.

Empirical Review

Munthali, R. (2006) investigated *traumatic ritual murders in Venda: A challenge to pastoral care*. The researcher employed both quantitative and qualitative designs in the study. This was a Masters' Degree Thesis intended to document in the department of pastoral theology what was considered a challenge to those who carry out the pastoral care giving as a profession. Using the Gerkin's case study method, the researcher explored two cases of families of (1) a lady beheaded and buried in the Church, (2) youth leader murdered because he protested against ritual murderers.

Nwankwo, U. V. & Okolie-Osemene, J. (2016) examined the *prevalence of lethal and non-lethal crimes in Nigeria*. The researchers connected trends and patterns of crimes in the 36 States. Their major source of information was Trent Online. This caused the researchers to use mostly media crime data statistics in the study. This method of data collection falls short of human touch in its analytical power. Qualitatively, the researcher used narratives of individuals to explore personal sharing of selected persons. NigeriaWatch.org provided the researchers a robust collection of news from major newspapers in the country.

Oyewole, S (2016) examined the title, *kidnapping for rituals: articles of faith and insecurity in Nigeria*. Although this study is not a pure empirical research, it has provided a powerful analytical tool for understanding the nexus between ritualists and kidnapers. To the researcher, two aspects of ritual motivated kidnapping are Faith and Materialism. Inside Faith the researcher presented religion, traditions and superstitions. In Materialism, he grouped fame, favour, protection, power, success and wealth. This research was a literary study relying on Dailies and Newspapers. It equally exposed the socio-political and economic underpinnings of kidnapping. Nevertheless, this study failed to provide evidence-based information on the correlations between oke-ite, ritual-killing and crude intelligence.

Olulowo, S. A. Babawale, S. T. & Anani, K. M. (2021) undertook to *examine the causes of kidnapping and its attendant challenges in Ogun State*. Their aim was to pin down the roles of schools, religion and government in the tackling of the problems of kidnapping. It highlighted the consequences and scrutinized the roles of schools, families, government and churches in tackling the problem of kidnapping. The paper submitted ritual crimes as one of the consequences of kidnapping. It used advanced theory of Strain as provided by Merton (1938) to give framework of his underpinnings. He also used Frustration-Aggression Theory of Dollan, (1939). In summary, these researchers tagged the causes of kidnapping to their presented three r's, namely *ransom, revenge and ritual*.

Summary of Literature Reviewed

Chapter Two reviewed literatures considered to be relevant to the study on oke-ite and ritual-killing as correlates of crude intelligence among youths in Anambra. Concepts of *oke-ite, ritual-killing, crude-intelligence, ritualism, retreatism, and fetishism*. Oke-ite is seen as a charm of concoction prepared in a mud pot for wealth, power and or fame. Unlike other charms, oke-ite is kept in the custody of the preparer for proper maintenance and ritual-servicing to the god or deity from whom, it is believed, the potency exudes. Oke-ite is concocted with parts or whole of humans, animals and herbs.

Ritual-killing is a practice of murdering a human being or animal for the purposes of sacrifice, money ritual or other gruesome reason. It is a crime against humanity and its dignity. Right to life is blatantly violated by ritual-killing. No amount of reasoning could explain the reason to take another's life for ritual purposes.

Crude intelligence is a destructive basic type of intelligence. It is an unrefined problem-solving and decision-making approach that prioritizes immediate gains, often through unethical or illegal means, without considering long-term consequences or the moral and societal impacts. It is a simplistic traditional ways of trivializing sophisticated problems as though the solution is easy, although very dangerous and disastrous in the long run.

Ritualism is a way of establishing norms and structures for the sake of conformity, even when these norms and structures do not yield desired outcomes. Ritualism also refers to actions taken for symbolic purposes, often based on superstitions or beliefs, like the practice of money rituals and oke-ite. Ritualism is a strict adherence to process rather than product. It could be traditional, religious, or superstitious sequential performance of rites.

Retreatism is a withdrawal from process conformity to the societal norms and ways of cultural beliefs. Retreatism rejects the goals and the means to achieve success through socially acceptable means. Fetishism refers to the attribution of inherent or supernatural powers to an object, material, or entity, which becomes the focus of obsessive attention or worship. It has various meanings in different fields such as anthropology, religion, sociology, and psychology.

Theories such as demonology, social learning, classical theory of crime and strain theory by Merton and by Agnew were reviewed. The framework of these theories and their connections to the study at hand were presented. Finally in the empirical studies, Munthali's study investigated traumatic ritual murders in Venda as challenge to pastoral care. Nwankwo and Okolie-Osemene examined the prevalence of lethal and non-lethal crimes in Nigeria. Another paper reviewed was that of Emmanuel which was on the rise of oke-ite ritual among the contemporary Igbo youth. Oyewole examined the title on kidnapping for rituals as articles of faith and insecurity in Nigeria. Olulowo, Babawale and Anani undertook to examine the causes of kidnapping and its attendant challenges in Ogun State. The last empirical paper reviewed was that of Salihu, H.; Isiaka, M. and Abdulaziz, I. (2019) who conducted a study on the growing phenomenon of money ritual-motivated killings in Nigeria which was an empirical investigation into the factors considered to be responsible.

RESEARCH METHOD

Research Design

A research design refers to the procedures used by the researcher to demonstrate an actual experience of those studied, how data is collected, analysed and reported. In this study explanatory correlation as well as descriptive survey is used.

Areas of the Study

This study was conducted in six Towns in the Three Senatorial Zones of Anambra State. The researcher assumed from earlier pilot study that oke-ite and ritual-killing are prevailing in this State. Anambra State is bordered by States of Delta, Imo, Abia and Enugu. The studied State is landlocked by Enugu State in the north and east, Delta State in the West, and Abia plus Imo States in the south. Each of the Senatorial Zones had seven (N=7) Local Government Areas (LGA) comprising the twenty one (21) LGAs in the State. South Senatorial Zone has fifty seven (N=57) towns; Central Senatorial Zone has fifty seven (N=57) towns plus the Metropolitan City of the Capital; and North Senatorial Zone has forty one (N=41) towns plus Onitsha commercial city north and south (*see Appendix C for details*). Anambra State has a landmass of 860KM² (2,200SqMiles) The study examined the practice of oke-ite and ritual-killing as together how these two variables correlated with the third variable of crude intelligence.

3.3 Population of the Study

According to Anambra Bureau of Statistics (2020) the population of Anambra State records 5,953,500 people. The target population for this study was youths in the State within the age range of 17–40 years. Male and female youths were studied. The same records presents that 55% of this Anambra State population constitutes the youth (N=3,274,425). The research included youths from different socio-economic backgrounds believed to have been individuals involved and experienced with those involved in oke-ite and ritual-killings. Under-cover application of basic and tactical Intels was employed in the selection of target population as well as priests of oke-ite.

Sample and Sampling Size

A multi-stage sampling procedure, comprising of simple random sampling technique and systematic sampling technique, was adopted for this study. Systematically, the following were sampled. Once the systematic sampling had been established, a random sampling was employed when the instruments were distributed to the youths. The sample size of this study is 1,200 participants. In determining the sample size, the researcher used Alien Taro Yamane (ATY, 1967) method of sampling the population to the studied. ATY, (1967) provides a simplified formula to calculate sample sizes and the formula was used to calculate the sample size for this study, as demonstrated below. 98% confidence was obtained in the sampling.

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument for data collection for the study was developed and validated questionnaires by the researcher. The researcher used Questionnaires and interview protocols for collection of primary data for this study. A Questionnaire of 40 items termed OIRK-Q (*Oke-ite and Ritual-killing Questionnaire*) was developed by the researcher.

Validity and Reliability of Instrument

The content and construct validity was used to validate the instrument. Content validity is the degree to which the test measured events as per objectives and research questions. Tichapondwa (2013) recommends that supervisors scrutinize items formulated to check if they match the requested criteria (clarity, intelligibility, neutrality among others). This is in line with suggestions by Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018) who argued that supervisors can be used to give objective opinions on contents of research instruments to ensure content and construct validity. Nonetheless, the researcher sought for additional two experts in the fields of Criminology and Crime Sciences. Including the supervisor's construct validation three experts scrutinized the questionnaire items related to their contents and construct validity.

A Test-retest reliability was used to ascertain a point of reliability, computed with the experts' validation scores plus one hundred (N=100) piloted data collected prior to the study (total=104). Test-retest

Reliability measures the consistency of results when one repeats the same test on the same sample at different point in time. 0.8 reliability index was obtained which was judged good for the study.

Method of Data Collection

The researcher trained six research assistants from the six towns of the Senatorial Districts using the Vigilante officers. Snowball means of distribution and collection was used to distribute and collect the data with the help of trained assistants. Copies of the Questionnaires distributed to the participants were retrieved through the same channel of distribution. Questionnaires were labelled Achalla = A1-210, Adazi-Nnukwu = B1-210, Igbo Ukwu = C1-210, Onitsha = D1-210, and Nkwelle-Ezunaka = E1-210, and Nnewi = F1-210. This labelling helped the researcher to mark data collection and avoid mix-up.

Each town collected centre received 210 OIRK-Q Questionnaires. From the returned OIRK-Qs, the researcher serially selected to use only fully completed Questionnaires. Once the selection of each town reached 200, the researcher could discard the rests of returned Questionnaires from each of the Towns. This was to maintain equality in the number of OIRK-Qs from the six Towns.

Method of Data Analysis

Simple percentage, Pearson R tool, frequency, and multivariate tools from Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) were used for data analyses. Where necessary, an Independent t-test and ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) tools were used for comparisons. At other places, Pearson Correlation Moment Coefficient and Multivariate tools were employed to test the hypotheses formulated. All the hypotheses were null and tested at p-value < 0.05 significant levels. This was done with the SPSS version 26.0. Descriptive analyses observed in the study were graphed, while computations from SPSS were presented in academic table formats as reported in the SPSS outputs.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The aim of this study was to examine oke-ite and ritual-killing as correlates of crude intelligence among youths of the five communities in Anambra State, Nigeria. The researcher observed from demographic information of participants in the OIRK-Q that the numbers of male and female participants are apart. Male N=732(61%) while female participants are N=468(39%). It did not surprise the researcher that more male youths participated in the study. Nonetheless, Lavenes' test of equality of variance revealed that this difference in the sample size did not affect the computed result of the data collected. More male youths are usually more zealous in the quest for money than their female counterparts. Therefore, it is not surprising that more male than female youths became involved in this study. Also, the three undercover in-depth interviews, conducted with the priests of oke-ite, revealed that all were young men. None of the participants was a woman despite the efforts to identify one. In the earlier studies of a Seminar presentation a study conducted in Oyi local government of Anambra State, the female youths participated in the studies more than the male youths (Chukwurah, 2023). The researcher observed that the youth between the age brackets of 17 – 25 have a great number of responses which is 900 (75%). This shows that the research work fulfilled its population target of the youth as it was demonstrated in table 4:1 of the research work. The demographic data also shows that the N = 252 (21%) of the youths between the ages of 26 – 30 equally responded. This presentation satisfied the researcher as the targeted age population participated.

The participants who reported that they have heard about crude intelligence were only seven. They completed the items on intelligence. However, when the prefix, *crude* was added to the construct, they were at a loss. The researcher believed that even the seven participants who responded 'YES' to their knowledge of crude intelligence did not in reality understand the true meaning of the phrasal word. The fact that participants claim they had never heard about crude intelligence that did not remove the knowledge which enabled them to participate fully in the answers about use of *intelligence* by the practitioners of oke-ite and ritual-killing.

Youths who are single registered a total N 972 (81%). This says that a greater number of the participants in this study have no family obligations towards dependants, meaning that they could be dependants themselves. Another surprise to the researcher was that the young people who checked that they are

traditional religion worshippers presented a higher than expected records (N = 276) which constituted 23% of the studied population. Ritualism finds rooting on traditional belief system. This might be the reason why the participants agreed that oke-ite ritual is not a fraud. In the same vein, this could also explain why the youths are more vulnerable in the hands of oke-ite priests (Oyewole, 2016; Evelyn, 2017). Belief is an important aspect of ritualism, according to Bell (1997) and Fontaine (2011). In this 21st Century, one wonders why gen-Z and immediate older would hold unto the belief system prior to the baby-boom generation of their fore parents. Traditional belief system does not provide commensurate hands-on for critical thinking and problem solving, confirming what Nwaka, (2020) spoke about in his writing on frivolities and fetishism. What it means is that youths have more time in hand than time engaged in learning and worthwhile ventures. When youths are less engaged, they have more time at hand to engage in frivolities and other peer influenced crimes.

In an attempt to answer research question one (RQ-1) “*How prevalent are oke-ite and ritual-killing among youth in Anambra State, Nigeria?*” the researcher observed that all the participants agreed that they *hear about oke-ite*. Their completion of items such as *rampant, common* and *hear daily news* to a higher agreeability shows that the phenomenon is prevalent. The researcher does not presume that all those who completed the OIRK-Q were those who practice oke-ite. That was the reason why efforts were made to interact with the oke-ite priests. Nonetheless, the researcher undertook to study the youths because it is believed that the customers and clients of oke-ite are the youths.

More participants responded to the disagreeability that oke-ite is a *fraud* or a crime (*disagreeability* = 620, *agreeability* = 550, *undecided* = 30). This met the researcher with surprise. The undercover interview with the oke-ite priests revealed a more surprising dynamic. All the three oke-ite priests posited that their activities were neither fraud nor crime of any sort. Those who were undecided about oke-ite also surprised the researcher. The question is this, ‘If oke-ite is not a crime, (as they contend that it is not) why secretive about it?’ A significant percentage of participants (N = 751, 62.6%) agreed that oke-ite is secretive, although not as high as ritual-killing. This dynamic tends to align with the works of Demonology scholars who opine that behaviours (even the most bizarre of them) could be justified through spiritual framework whether right or wrong (Ziolkowski, 1991; Tepperman, 2010; Trefilovia, 2020).

Another characteristic of this oke-ite study is that the participants’ responses revealed an agreeability that oke-ite is a *sacrifice* (99.3%) more than they agree that ritual-killing is a sacrifice. This surprising revelation insinuates that the studied youth agree that most of the practices of oke-ite include a form of sacrifice with human beings, animals and or herbs. This maintains an agreement that oke-ite is a ritual. Every sacrifice carries aspects of ritual between the start to finish of it, but not all rituals are sacrifice. The concoction of oke-ite entails sacrificing living things – humans, animals (parts or whole) and or herbs. If non-living things are part of oke-ite such as stone, sand and so on, then these are not considered as sacrifice. They form edification for the sacrifice.

In answer to research three about the *characteristics of ritual-killing*, participants, apparently, had no doubts as they identified salient characteristics of ritual-killing. Paramount to the issues raised, participants underscored the following characteristics with high degree of agreeability, namely *associated to kidnapping, crime, secrecy, peer influence* and *humans used*. Unlike oke-ite (33.4%), ritual-killing (92.3%) was highly associated to kidnapping practices in the State and they have no doubt as to whether ritual-killing is a crime (N = 1,199; 99.9%). Only one participant disagreed that ritual-killing is a crime which again surprised the researcher. The priests of the oke-ite interviewed said that if the charm requirement is human parts, then human parts would be used for the oke-ite. Meanwhile, they do not see oke-ite as a crime. The question of ritual-killing being a crime was not answered. They chose to remain silent.

In the case of oke-ite and ritual-killing, youths may develop justifications that align with crude intelligence, such as rationalizing their actions as necessary for survival or success in an unjust world. For instance, a young person may come to believe that the socioeconomic system is rigged against them and that engaging in ritual crime or fraud is a valid way to “even the playing field.” This rationalization is

learned from observing others who successfully use these practices and from the cultural narratives that support such beliefs.

Youths learn these ritual crime behaviours through socialization processes, including family teachings, community practices, and peer influences. Normalization and socialization go hand in hand. The normalization of Oke-ite practices among peers and community members can create an environment where engaging in fraud or ritual crime is viewed as acceptable, further perpetuating the cycle of such behaviour. Crude intelligence plays a role here as youths may rationalize their actions through the lens of their cultural beliefs, failing to see the ethical implications of their choice.

A young man in a community where ritual crime is prevalent may observe older peers or community members engaging in oke-ite practices and gaining wealth quickly. Over time, he internalizes the belief that performing rituals is an effective and acceptable way to achieve success. His role models—perhaps a local spiritualist or a wealthy individual involved in ritual crime—serve as powerful influences. When faced with financial hardship and social pressure to succeed, he turns to these observed behaviours, justifying them with the belief that this is the quickest and most effective path to wealth. His decision-making is influenced by the reinforcement he observes in his community, where those who engage in these practices are celebrated rather than punished.

Peer influence, (82.6%) as a characteristic of ritual-killing, shows high rate of responses among the youths of Anambra State. High profiled crimes such as ritual-killing are learned. Studies of ritual-killing presented by scholars such as Oriabure, (2023); Isiaka and Nasirudeen, (2018) are traceable to a form of repetition that increases in professionalization. This makes ritual-killing not a rampant practice, except in Nigeria where government and security bodies seem to do nothing about ritual crimes. It is learned practice. No one wakes up and decides to be a ritual-killer. Peer pressure places tremendous impact on the first timers in this crime. Intake of hard drug and harmful substance predispose the ritual-killers to the state of becoming hardened in criminality. Social learning theory critically applies in practice of this crime practice. Unlearning and control of this crime is possible. Curbing of any crime is a matter of using classical deterrence as suggested by Raskolnikov, (2021). Besides, Baumeister and Boone (2007) have opined that control, hard-work and moral strength could be learned and trained in the youth as ways to curtail ritual crimes.

If participants in this study responded that practitioners of Oke-ite are intelligent, that means that imparting the habit of control and moral strength could be done on the practitioners of this fraud. It is usually easy for an intelligent person to learn or unlearn. Education and community organizing could be used to control the customers' influx to the services of Oke-ite. Classical deterrence could be used by government and community security outfits to clamp down ritual-killing practice. In relation to oke-ite and ritual-killing, Classical theory is applied to understand how youths make decisions to engage in these practices, particularly in the context of crude intelligence.

Crude intelligence and simplistic problem-solving crude intelligence, in this context, refers to the simplistic, unethical, and short-term approach to problem-solving and decision-making. Social Learning theory suggests that youths with crude intelligence may be more susceptible to engaging in oke-ite practices because they are easily swayed by observed behaviours that promise quick results. Rather than critically analysing the long-term consequences of their actions, such as the legal or moral ramifications of fraud and ritual crime, these youths focus on the immediate benefits—wealth, status, and social recognition. This reflects the unrefined cognitive process behind crude intelligence, where ethical considerations are disregarded in favour of short-term rewards.

A young man in Nigeria may find himself facing financial struggles and observes peers engaging in oke-ite rituals, gaining wealth quickly. He conducts a mental cost-benefit analysis and concludes that participating in these rituals provides a faster, easier route to financial stability compared to traditional employment, which appears slow and uncertain. Lacking the foresight to consider potential legal ramifications or ethical implications, he rationalizes that the rewards justify the risks, illustrating how Classical theory explains his decision to engage in oke-ite fraud.

Crime is product of a deliberate, rational, hedonistically calculated decision by the criminal. The criminal decides to engage in crime because he calculates that engagement in law breaking (crime) will bring him pleasure and benefits. Following this logic, classical theorists argue first and foremost that because the criminal has freely and viciously chosen to commit crime, he deserves to be punished. Secondly, that in order to deter people from committing crime, such kind and severity (amount) of punishment as will counter-balance or wipe off the gains or pleasure derivable from a crime should be assigned to each crime. That is to say, people will be discouraged from engaging in criminal conduct only when the punishment prescribed for each criminal act surpasses the anticipated gains (pleasure) from that criminal act.

Classical theory of crime causation rests-squarely on two core concepts espoused by these early criminologists. These are the concepts of 'will power' and 'hedonism': the theorists borrowed from psychology and philosophy. Classical theory argues that every human being possesses a will, that is, both free and powerful. Decision-making and choice-making use the faculty of will. This means that man is a free moral agent, and that behaviour is purposive and intentionally acted out by actors. Furthermore, the theory argues that human beings are hedonistic creatures. That is, man by his nature always seeks to obtain pleasure and to avoid pain; or, at his best, to maximize pleasure and minimize pain. The pleasure-pain principle implies that human beings act deliberately and rationally, and choose those actions which give them pleasure, while avoiding those other actions which produce pain.

CONCLUSION

The study conducted across six Towns in Anambra State, Nigeria—Achalla, AdaziNnukwu, Igbo Ukwu, Onitsha, Nkwelle-Ezunaka and Nnewi—shows that Oke-ite practice and ritual-killing together have slight significant correlations with crude intelligence; but Oke-ite alone has high significant relationship with crude intelligence. When two of them interacted in correlations with crude intelligence, slight correlation exists.

Although, as observed from the computation in Table 4:7, there is significant difference between the means Oke-ite $_{\mu}$ =34.2 and Ritual-killing $_{\mu}$ =18.04 in Table 4:7, Table 4:8 shows significant relationship. The analytic interpretation is that those who rated low in certain *items* of Oke-ite, rated low in similar *items* of Ritual-killing variable, vice versa. This provides internal consistency among the youth respondents to the OIRK-Q. In general, participants' responses to the items of oke-ite and ritual-killing show significant relationships between the two variables. This goes to say that oke-ite is a ritual as well as ritual-killing and the two have qualities that expose them to being a criminal offence.

However, participants, in their responses, believe that oke-ite is not a fraud but that ritual-killing is a crime. Observation of studied oke-ite priests insinuates that even use of humans in their concoction of oke-ite is not considered crime. Further interviews showed that if human parts are used in preparation of Oke-ite charm, then the ritual becomes a crime; but if it was not used to prepare such charm that it is not a crime. One wonders how to monitor oke-ite concoction process when the priests themselves have agreed that oke-ite, prepared with humans or not, is neither a fraud nor a crime. Oke-Ite practices, which often involve rituals, are believed to bring wealth. They are reinforced through cultural narratives and superstitions. In communities where ritual crime is normalized, youths may grow up in environments where the belief in magic or spiritual manipulation is pervasive.

Youths may be taught that engaging in these rituals is a necessary step to attract wealth or to appease spirits, creating a cultural framework that legitimizes such actions. In agreement with Baumeister and Boone, (2007) self-control is learnable and training in this construct is possible. In the context of oke-ite, youths may believe that their problems can be solved through supernatural means, bypassing the need for hard work, education, or ethical considerations. But this belief can be changed.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study on OIRK in Anambra State revealed that social factors including poverty, love of money, lack of mortality, and lack of social support influences ritual crimes among the population. To enhance the implementation, the following recommendations are proposed

1. The Federal and state government should checkmate the activities of the traditional native doctors that promote ritual crimes of all sorts.
2. Parents, schools and religious leaders should teach their children and pupils that morality is more important than money.
3. Schools should stop under-aged from coming into school premises with their personal property such as cars and expensive phones.
4. The society should develop a way of helping the youths and asking questions as to their source of wealth before appreciating them in any shape or form.
5. The religious leaders should work on individual spiritual lives rather than the gifts they offer in different religious settings.
6. Affective domain curriculum should become a very important and gradable aspect of learning going on in Junior and Secondary levels of education in the State.

Limitation of the Study

This study, while insightful, has limitations that should be acknowledged.

Geographic Limitation: The study was confined Anambra State, Nigeria, and therefore may not reflect the accurate information in a larger society of the Nation.

Sampling Bias: The study focused on limited number six towns in one State which may not fully represent the diversity of cultural belief in the Country. This restricts the generalizability of the findings to all the States in the South East, much less Nigeria.

Self-reported data: The data collected were based on self-reports from categories of youths in Anambra state, Nigeria which may be subject to biases.

Lack of qualitative data: The study primarily relied on quantitative data and parsimonious sample of three for qualitative study. This sample was rather too small. A more detailed exploration of individual experiences could provide additional insights.

These limitations suggest the need for future studies to address these gaps so as to provide a more comprehensive understanding of oke-ite and ritual-killing as together these two correlate with intelligence.

Because the topic is a relatively new area of study, there was no much research work that is relevant to this study. Therefore, the researcher could not get enough empirical work to review as stipulated by the school of postgraduate studies regulation.

5.5 Suggested Further Studies

Future studies could expand on this research by exploring the negative impact of ritual killings in our society. Additionally, qualitative research could delve deeper into the experiences and perspectives of students, to provide a richer understanding of the challenges of oke-ite and ritual-killings. A comparative study across different regions or tribes with varying socio-political environments could also offer valuable insights into this emerging phenomenon. Furthermore, investigating the activities of traditional worshippers and spiritual leaders such as pastors and native doctors could be a promising area for future research.

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